

Stereoselective total synthesis of seimatopolide A[†]

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Abstract : Stereoselective total synthesis of the naturally occurring bioactive macrolide, seimatopolide A has been achieved starting from commercially available (+)-diethyl tartrate. Chelation-controlled Grignard reaction, Yamaguchi esterification, ring closing cross metathesis and CBS reduction reactions are involved as key steps.

Keywords : Seimatopolide A, total synthesis, Grignard reaction, Yamaguchi esterification, ring closing metathesis, CBS reduction.

Introduction

In 2012, Lee and co-workers isolated two new polyhydroxylated macrolides seimatopolide A (**1**) and seimatopolide B (**2**) from the ethyl acetate extract of the fungal culture medium of *Seimatosporium discosioides*¹. The structures of these natural products have been established from their corresponding spectroscopic data including 1D and 2D NMR spectral values. The modified Mosher's method was initially used to establish the absolute configurations of seimatopolide A as (3*R*,6*R*,7*R*,9*S*) and seimatopolide B as (3*R*,6*S*,9*S*). However, subsequently the structure of seimatopolide A (**1**) has been revised as (3*S*,6*S*,7*S*,9*R*) by re-investigation of its analytical and spectral data² as well as by syntheses³. Seimatopolides A (**1**) and B (**2**) activated peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR)- γ with EC₅₀ values of 1.15 and 11.05 μ M, respectively¹. The peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) are a group of nuclear proteins which work as transcription factor regulating the expression of genes. As per recent studies, PPAR- γ is the potential therapeutic target for the type II diabetes, inflammatory disease and certain cancers⁴. Seimatopolide A also moderately reduced the expression of two gluconeogenic genes, glucose-6-phosphatase (G6Pase) and phosphoenol pyruvate carboxykinase (PEPCK), suggesting that the com-

ound is a possible therapeutic candidate as an antidiabetic drug¹.

These structural and biological profiles attracted us for the total synthesis of this compound. In continuation of our work on the construction of naturally bioactive molecules⁵, herein we report the stereoselective total synthesis of seimatopolide A (**1**) through an alternative simple and efficient route.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.
Part 70 in the series, "Synthetic studies on natural products".

Results and discussion

The retro synthetic analysis for seimatopolide A 1 (Scheme 1) revealed that the compound could be prepared by ring closing metathesis of the diene precursor 3 which could be obtained by the Yamaguchi esterification of the two key fragments, alcohol fragment 4 and acid fragment 5. The desired alcohol 4 fragment could be produced from (+)-diethyl tartrate through the formation of the cyano-compound 11, followed by regioselective Grignard reaction. On the other hand, the requisite acid fragment 5 could be prepared from commercially available propane-1,3-diol through Corey-Bakshi-Shibata reduction reaction.

The synthesis of the alcohol fragment 4 started (Scheme 2) from (+)-diethyl tartrate which was subjected to acetonide protection with 2,2-DMP in the presence of *p*-TSA in CH_2Cl_2 , followed by reduction of the ester groups with DIBAL-H to afford the diol 6 in 79% yield

over two steps. The diol was subjected to monoprotection with TBSCl in the presence of NaH in THF to produce the alcohol 7 (89% yield). The oxidation of primary alcohol 7 under Swern oxidation conditions led to the corresponding aldehyde which was subsequently reacted with one carbon ylide (generated from $\text{CH}_3\text{PPh}_3\text{Br}$, *n*-BuLi in THF) to form the olefin 8 (71% yield). Desilylation of 8 using TBAF in THF, followed by tosylation using TsCl in the presence of Et_3N /DMAP (cat.) in CH_2Cl_2 furnished the tosylated compound 9 in 80% yield over two steps. The treatment of NaCN/NaI (cat.) to the tosylated compound 9 in acetone did not furnish the cyanated compound. Next, the tosylated compound 9 was subjected to iodination using NaI in acetone under reflux to afford the iodo compound 10 which underwent cyanation using NaCN in DMSO to generate the cyanated compound 11 in 81% yield over two steps. The cyano group was then converted to aldehydes (90% yield) using DBAL-H in CH_2Cl_2

Scheme 1. Retrosynthetic analysis for seimatopolide A.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of fragment 4.

Reagent and conditions : (a) (i) 2,2-DMP, *p*-TSA, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C to r.t., 6 h, 86%, (ii) DIBAL-H, CH₂Cl₂, -78 °C, 30 min, 92%; (b) NaH, TBSCl, THF, 0 °C to r.t., 2 h, 89%; (c) (i) (COCl)₂, DMSO, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, -78 °C to r.t., 2 h, 93%, (ii) CH₃PPh₃⁺Br⁻, *n*-BuLi, THF, -78 °C to r.t., 4 h, 71%; (d) (i) TBAF, THF, 0 °C to r.t. 6 h, 88%, (ii) TsCl, Et₃N, DMAP (cat.), CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C to r.t., 2 h, 91%; (e) NaI, acetone, reflux, 3 h, 87%; (f) NaCN, DMSO, 0 °C to r.t., 6 h, 92%; (g) (i) DIBAL-H, CH₂Cl₂, -78 °C, 30 min, 90%, (ii) C₉H₁₉MgBr, diethyl ether, -20 °C, 4 h, 82%.

and subsequently the aldehyde was treated with nine-carbon magnesium salt (generated from Mg and C₉H₁₉Br in ether) for Grignard reaction to furnish the alcohol **4** along with its separable diastereoisomer in 85 : 15 ratio in 82% yield⁶. The desired alcohol **4** has been utilized for the subsequent steps.

The synthesis of requisite acid fragment **5** was started from commercially available 1,3-propane diol (Scheme 3). The monoprotection of the diol using 4-methoxybenzyl chloride in the presence of NaH/TBAI (cat.) in THF led to monoprotected alcohol **12** in 86% yield. The primary alcohol **12** was then subjected to oxidation using PCC in CH₂Cl₂ to aldehydes (91% yield) which was reacted with vinyl magnesium bromide in THF to lead the secondary alcohol **13** in 83% yield. The alcohol **13** was then converted to vinyl ketone **14** using IBX in DMSO/CH₂Cl₂ in 91% yield. Enantioselective reduction of this vinyl ketone **14** using *S*-(-)-2-methyl oxaborolidine and BH₃.Me₂S in THF (Corey-Bakshi-Shibata reduction) afforded the secondary alcohol **15** in 93% yield⁷. The alcohol was then subjected to TBS protection using TBSCl/imidazole (cat.)

in DMF to produce the silyl ether **16** in 95% yield. Deprotection of PMB ether was achieved using DDQ in CH₂Cl₂ to furnish the primary alcohol **17** (91% yield)⁸. Finally the oxidation of alcohol to acid **5** was accomplished using TEMPO/BAIB in CH₂Cl₂/H₂O in 89% yield⁹.

Having both the fragments, alcohol **4** and acid **5** in hand, they were subjected to esterification (Scheme 4) under Yamaguchi reaction condition (2,4,6-trichlorobenzoyl chloride, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, DMAP, toluene)¹⁰ to lead to the ester precursor **3** in 88% yield. It was then treated with 2nd generation Grubbs' catalyst (20 mol%) to bring about the ring closing metathesis¹¹ to produce the macrolide **18** (87% yield). Finally, both the protecting groups, acetamide and TBS were deprotected simultaneously using TFA in CH₂Cl₂ to give the seimatopolide A (**1**) (81% yield). All the spectroscopic (¹H, ¹³C NMR and Mass) data of synthetic seimatopolide A (**1**) were in full agreement with the natural product^{1,2}.

In conclusion, we have achieved the total synthesis of natural seimatopolide A through an alternative and effi-

Scheme 3. Synthesis of fragment 5.

Reagent and conditions : (a) NaH, THF, 0 °C to r.t., 6 h, 86%; (b) (i) PCC, 4 Å MS, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C to r.t., 2 h, 91%, (ii) CH₂=CHMgBr, THF, 0 °C to r.t., 2 h, 83%; (c) IBX, DMSO/CH₂Cl₂, r.t., 91%; (d) CBS reduction, *S*-(-)-2-methyloxaborolidine BH₃·Me₂S, THF, -30 °C, 2 h, 93%; (e) TBSCl, imidazole/DMAP (cat.), DMF, 0 °C to r.t., 3 h, 95%; (f) DDQ, CH₂Cl₂/H₂O, 0 °C to r.t., 4 h, 91%; (g) TEMPO/BAIB, CH₂Cl₂/H₂O, 0 °C to r.t., 5 h, 89%.

Scheme 4. Coupling of fragments 4 and 5 to synthesise seimatopolide A.

Reagent and conditions : (a) 5, 2,4,6-trichlorobenzoyl chloride, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C to r.t., 1 h, 88%, then 4, DMAP, toluene, r.t., 3 h, 86%; (b) Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst 20 mol%, CH₂Cl₂ reflux, 12 h, 87%; (c) TFA, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C to r.t., 10 h, 81%.

cient approach starting from relatively inexpensive (+)-diethyl tartrate and propane-1,3-diol by applying regioselective Grignard reaction, CBS reduction, ring closing metathesis reactions and Yamaguchi esterification.

Experimental

General Experimental procedure : The silica gel F₂₅₄ plates were used for thin layer chromatography (TLC) in which the spots were examined under UV light and then

developed by an iodine vapor. Column chromatography (CC) was performed with silica gel (BDH 100–200 mesh). Solvents were purified according to standard procedures. The spectra were recorded with the following instruments; IR : Perkin-Elmer RX FT-IR spectrophotometer; NMR : Varian Gemini 200 MHz (^1H) and 50 MHz (^{13}C) spectrometer; ESIMS : VG-Autospec micromass. Organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

((4R, 5R)-2, 2-Dimethyl-1, 3-dioxolane-4, 5-diyldimethanol (6) : To a stirring solution of (+)-diethyl tartrate (2.06 g, 10 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (30 ml) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (10 mL, 80 mmol), *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (175 mg, 1 mmol) was added at 0 °C and stirred for another 6 h at room temperature. After completion of the reaction, as indicated by TLC, the mixture was kept at 0 °C and quenched with aqueous saturated NaHCO_3 solution (50 ml). The mixture was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 10 ml) and organic layer dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by CC (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1) to give (4*S*,5*S*)-diethyl-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxolane-4,5-dicarboxylate as colourless oil (2.115 g, 86%). $R_f = 0.5$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +24.8$ (*c* 0.5, MeOH); IR (neat) : 2988, 2947, 1761, 1448, 1251 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 4.63 (2H, s), 4.19 (4H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz), 1.41 (6H, s), 1.26 (6H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 169.0, 113.5, 76.7, 61.0, 26.2, 14.2; ESIMS : m/z 246 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 269 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

To a stirring solution of the ester compound prepared above (1.605 g, 6.5 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (30 ml) under inert atmosphere of nitrogen, DIBAL-H (18.3 mL, [1.6 (*M*) in hexane], 29.3 mmol) was added at -78 °C and stirred for 30 min. After completion of reaction (TLC), the mixture was warmed to 0 °C and quenched with saturated aqueous solution of $\text{KNaC}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, followed by stirring for another 4 h until the layer was separated. The mixture was then extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 10 ml) and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The extract was concentrated under reduce pressure and purified by CC (hexane/EtOAc = 3 : 7) to give product **6** as colourless oil (972 mg, 92%). $R_f = 0.5$ (hexane/EtOAc = 2 : 8); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +19.7$ (*c* 0.5, MeOH); IR (neat) : 3395, 2991, 2927, 1365, 1264, 1251 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.99–3.90 (2H, m), 3.79–3.68 (4H, m), 1.41 (6H, s);

^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 110.0, 78.9, 62.3, 26.5; ESIMS : m/z 163 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 185 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

*((4R, 5R)-5-(((*t*-Butyldimethylsilyl)oxy)methyl)-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)methanol (7)* : Sodium hydride (200 mg, 60% dispersion in mineral oil, 5.0 mmol) was taken in round bottom flux under inert atmosphere of nitrogen and dry THF (20 mL) was added to it at 0 °C. After 5 min the compound **6** (830 mg, 5.1 mmol) was dissolved in dry THF (10 mL) and consequently added dropwise to it. The mixture was stirred for another 1 h at 0 °C and then *t*-butyldimethylsilyl chloride (1.405 g, 5.6 mmol) was added and vigorous stirring was continued for additional 1 h. After completion of reaction (TLC), the mixture was quenched with saturated aqueous solution of NH_4Cl at 0 °C and extracted with EtOAc (3 × 10 mL). The organic extract was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduce pressure and purified by CC (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1) to give product **7** as colourless oil (1.23 g, 89%). $R_f = 0.5$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +13.7$ (*c* 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 3470, 2985, 2928, 2860, 1473, 1461, 1377, 1257 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.98 (1H, m), 3.92–3.84 (2H, m), 3.80–3.63 (3H, m), 2.51 (1H, brs), 1.42 (3H, s), 1.40 (3H, s), 0.90 (9H, s), 0.09 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 109.4, 80.6, 78.2, 64.0, 63.0, 27.6, 27.0, 26.0, 18.8, -5.0; ESIMS : m/z 277 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 299 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

t-Butyl-(((4*R*,5*R*)-2,2-dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)methoxy)dimethylsilane (8) : To a solution of oxaly chloride (0.44 mL, 4.8 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (10 mL), DMSO (0.90 mL, 12.8 mmol) was added dropwise at -78 °C and the resulting mixture was stirred for 5 min. A solution of alcohol **7** (1.104 g, 4.0 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 was added dropwise to it and stirred for additional 30 min. Et_3N (2.8 mL, 20 mmol) was then added to the mixture and allowed to keep at room temperature and stirred for another 30 min. The reaction mixture was quenched with saturated aqueous solution of NH_4Cl at 0 °C and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 10 ml). The organic extract was washed with H_2O and brine and dried over Na_2SO_4 , followed by concentration under reduced pressure and purification by flash chromatography (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1) to give the aldehydes (1.02 g, 93%) as pale yellow oil.

To a solution of methyl triphenylphosphonium bro-

mide (16 mmol) in dry THF (15 mL), *n*-BuLi (1.6 M in hexanes, 7.5 mL, 12 mmol) was added at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and stirred for 1 h. The above aldehyde (945 mg, 3.5 mmol) in THF (10 mL) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was slowly warmed to room temperature and stirred for 6 h. The mixture was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH_4Cl (10 mL) at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The resulting biphasic mixture was extracted with ether ($3 \times 10\text{ mL}$) and the combined organic layers were washed with H_2O (10 mL) and brine (10 mL), then dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue was purified by flash chromatography (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 98 : 2) to give olefin **8** (952 mg, 71%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.7$ (hexane/EtOAc = 19 : 1); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -9.6$ (*c* 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2985, 2928, 2860, 1473, 1461, 1377, 1257 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.87 (1H, m), 5.36 (1H, d, *J* 17.3 Hz), 5.23 (1H, d, *J* 10.5 Hz), 4.34 (1H, m), 3.80–3.72 (3H, m), 1.43 (3H, s), 1.42 (3H, s), 0.90 (9H, s), 0.07 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 135.8, 117.9, 109.0, 81.3, 79.2, 62.5, 30.0, 26.8, 25.8, -5.4 ; ESIMS : m/z $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

((*4R,5R*)-2,2-Dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)methyl-4-methylbenzenesulfonate (**9**) : To a solution of **8** (805 mg, 2.95 mmol) in THF (5 mL), TBAF (1 M in THF (14.75 mL, 14.8 mmol) was added dropwise at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The resulting brown solution was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. The reaction was then quenched with saturated aqueous NH_4Cl (5 mL) and extracted with EtOAc ($3 \times 10\text{ mL}$). The combined organic layer was washed with brine (15 mL), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 90 : 10) to give ((*4R,5R*)-2,2-dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)methanol (410 mg, 88%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.4$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -17.3$ (*c* 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 3471, 2988, 2921, 2860, 1467, 1473, 1381, 1257 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.83 (1H, m), 5.38 (1H, m), 5.26 (1H, m), 4.31 (1H, m), 3.85–3.76 (2H, m), 3.59 (1H, m), 1.43 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 143.9, 119.1, 109.2, 81.0, 78.3, 67.6, 29.6, 26.9; ESIMS : m/z 159 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 181 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

To a stirring solution of the alcohol prepared above

(395 mg, 2.5 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (10 mL), Et_3N (1.75 mL, 12.5 mmol) was added at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under inert atmosphere of nitrogen. After 5 min, *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (765 mg, 4 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) was added dropwise at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then catalytic amount of DMAP (30 mg, 0.22 mmol) was added to it and stirred for additional 2 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the mixture was quenched with saturated aqueous solution of NH_4Cl at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The organic layer was extracted with EtOAc ($3 \times 10\text{ mL}$), washed with H_2O and brine and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the crude residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (hexane : EtOAc = 5 : 1) to yield **9** (720 mg, 91%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.6$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -13.7$ (*c* 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2985, 2928, 2853, 1473, 1462, 1377, 1257 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.35 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 5.78 (1H, m), 5.39–5.23 (2H, m), 4.27–4.15 (2H, m), 4.08 (1H, m), 3.85 (1H, m), 2.46 (3H, s), 1.39 (3H, s), 1.36 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 145.1, 136.1, 134.2, 129.9, 128.0, 119.0, 118.1, 109.9, 78.8, 78.0, 67.9, 26.9, 26.6, 21.6; ESIMS : m/z 313 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 335 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(*4S,5R*)-4-(Iodomethyl)-2,2-dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolane (**10**) : To a solution of the tosylate **9** (690 mg, 2.2 mmol), sodium iodide (831 mg, 5.5 mmol) in acetone (10 mL) was added and the mixture refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was evaporated, water (50 mL) was added, and the resulting solution was extracted with ether ($3 \times 10\text{ mL}$). The combined organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (hexane : EtOAc = 12 : 1) to give **10** (510 mg, 87% yield) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.6$ (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -10.3$ (*c* 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2986, 2931, 2860, 1473, 1467, 1372, 1257, 1005 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.86 (1H, m), 5.42 (1H, m), 5.30 (1H, m), 4.17 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 3.64 (1H, m), 3.34 (1H, dd, *J* 11.2, 5.1 Hz), 3.23 (1H, dd, *J* 10.3, 5.1 Hz), 1.48 (3H, s), 1.43 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 134.9, 119.5, 82.8, 79.1, 27.3, 4.5; ESIMS : m/z 269 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$.

2-((*4R,5R*)-2,2-Dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)acetonitrile (**11**) : To a solution of the iodide **10** (470

mg, 1.75 mmol) in dry DMSO (5 mL), sodium cyanide (155 mg, 3.15 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 6 h at room temperature. Water (15 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and the resulting solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 10 mL), washed with brine (10 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The crude residue was concentrated under reduced pressure and was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel to afford nitrile **11** (270 mg, 92%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.5$ (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -6.9$ (c 0.5, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 2988, 2955, 2928, 2856, 2253, 1468, 1463, 1371, 1255 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 5.83 (1H, m), 5.48 (1H, m), 5.36 (1H, m), 4.24 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 3.91–3.82 (1H, m), 2.76 (1H, dd, *J* 17.3, 5.2 Hz), 2.58 (1H, dd, *J* 17.3, 5.2 Hz), 1.48 (3H, s), 1.45 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 133.4, 120.6, 116.1, 110.2, 81.7, 75.2, 26.9, 26.7, 20.2; ESIMS : *m/z* 168 [M+H]⁺.

(R)-1-((4*R*,5*R*)-2,2-Dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)undecan-2-ol (**4**) : To a stirred solution of the nitrile **11** (245 mg, 1.45 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (4 mL), DIBAL-H (1.6 *M*) in hexane, 1 ml, 1.6 mmol) was added dropwise at -78 °C. The solution was stirred at -78 °C for 30 min, and the reaction was quenched by addition of saturated aqueous sodium potassium tartrate (10 mL). The mixture was warmed to room temperature and diluted with CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL). The resulting mixture was stirred until two clear layers were observed. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 10 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. The resulting crude aldehyde (225 mg, 90% yield) was carried onto the next step without further purification.

Pre-activated magnesium (288 mg, 12 mmol) was taken in a round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser under inert atmosphere of nitrogen and dry diethyl ether (15 mL) was added to it at room temperature. Then C₉H₁₉Br (1.71 mL, 10 mmol) was added slowly to magnesium mixture at room temperature and the Grignard reagent was generated indicating the heating and reflux of the mixture. After completion of generation of Grignard reagent, the mixture was cooled to -20 °C and a solution of aldehyde (1.2 mmol), prepared above, in diethyl ether (5 mL) was added slowly and stirred for 4 h at -20 °C.

After completion of reaction (TLC), the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated aqueous solution of NH₄Cl at 0 °C. The organic layer was extracted with EtOAc (3 × 10 ml), washed with H₂O and brine and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the crude residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (hexane : EtOAc = 5 : 1) and major diastereoisomer was separated to yield of alcohol **4** (235 mg, 82%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.3$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -5.3$ (c 0.5, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 3531, 2928, 2859, 1757, 1473, 1467, 1373, 1252 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 5.82 (1H, m), 5.37 (1H, m), 5.26 (1H, m), 4.07 (1H, m), 3.98–3.85 (2H, m), 2.30 (1H, brs), 1.75–1.65 (2H, m), 1.50–1.45 (2H, m), 1.42 (3H, s), 1.41 (3H, s), 1.35–1.23 (14H, m), 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 134.8, 119.1, 109.2, 82.0, 77.5, 68.5, 37.7, 31.6, 29.5, 29.2, 29.6, 27.3, 26.8, 26.5, 25.8, 22.8, 14.0; ESIMS : *m/z* 299 [M+H]⁺, 321 [M+Na]⁺.

3-((4-Methoxybenzyl)oxy)propan-1-ol (**12**) : To a stirred suspension of NaH (168 mg, 60% dispersion in mineral oil, 4.2 mmol) in THF (25 mL) propane, 1,3-diol (3.8 mmol) was added at 0 °C. The mixture was stirred for 1 h and TBAI (30 mg, 0.03 mmol) and 4-methoxybenzyl chloride (0.52 mL, 3.8 mmol) were added. The mixture was stirred for 12 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the mixture was quenched with ice and extracted with EtOAc (3 × 10 mL). The combined organic layer was concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by CC to furnish **12** (630 mg, 86%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.3$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); IR (neat) : 1675, 1517, 1467, 1253 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.22 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 6.83 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.41 (2H, s), 3.79 (3H, s), 3.73–3.66 (2H, m), 3.59–3.54 (2H, m), 2.52 (1H, brs), 1.83–1.73 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 159.8, 130.1, 128.7, 114.4, 72.8, 68.2, 59.4, 55.9, 32.1; ESIMS : *m/z* 197 [M+H]⁺.

5-((4-Methoxybenzyl)oxy)pent-1-en-3-ol (**13**) : To a stirring solution of alcohol **12** (860 mg, 2.9 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (15 mL), celite (500 mg) and pyridinium chlorochromate (1.56 g, 7.25 mmol) were added at 0 °C. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. After completion of reaction (TLC), the mixture was filtered through celite pad and the filtrate was concentrated and subjected

to flash chromatography to afford the aldehyde (535 mg, 91%) which was carried onto the next step.

To a stirring solution of aldehyde (514 mg, 2.65 mmol) in dry THF (15 mL), vinyl magnesium bromide (3.3 mL, 1.6 M) in THF, 5.3 mmol) was added at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h. After completion of reaction (TLC), the reaction was quenched by saturated aqueous solution of NH_4Cl (10 mL) and the organic phase extracted with EtOAc (3×10 mL). The combined organic mixture was concentrated and purified by CC (490 mg, 83%) to afford the allylic alcohol **13**. The spectral data were same as for the compound **15** described below.

5-((4-Methoxybenzyl)oxy)pent-1-en-3-one (14): To an ice cold solution of IBX in DMSO alcohol **13** (440 mg, 1.98 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) was added. The mixture was stirred for 4 h, diluted with CH_2Cl_2 and filtered through celite pad. The filtrate was washed with NaHCO_3 solution, water and brine. The combined mixture was concentrated and purified by flash chromatography to furnish ketone **14** (396 mg, 91%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.5$ (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1); IR (neat) : 3420, 2933, 2843, 1621, 1590, 1520, 1256 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 7.55 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.85 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.32 (1H, m), 5.88 (1H, dd, J 17.2, 2.3 Hz), 5.22 (1H, dd, J 10.5, 2.3 Hz), 4.49 (2H, s), 3.87 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 2.94 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50 MHz) : δ 198.5, 159.5, 136.0, 129.5, 129.2, 127.7, 114.0, 72.5, 64.5, 55.5, 45.2; ESIMS : m/z 243 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(S)-5-((4-Methoxybenzyl)oxy)pent-1-en-3-ol (15): To a stirred solution of (*R*)-Me-CBS (1 M) solution in toluene (0.5 mL, 0.49 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL), $\text{BH}_3\cdot\text{BDS}$ (5 M) solution in THF (0.38 mL, 1.80 mmol) was added at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the mixture was cooled to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then the keto compound **14** (365 mg, 1.63 mmol) in dry THF (5 mL) was added and stirred for additional 2 h. After completion of reaction (TLC), the reaction was quenched with MeOH at same temperature. The MeOH was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with EtOAc (3×10 mL), washed with water and brine. The combined extract was concentrated and purified by CC to furnish the alcohol **15** (335 mg, 93%). $R_f = 0.4$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +13.7$ (c 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 3420, 2933, 2843, 1621, 1590, 1520, 1256

cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 7.27 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.89 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 5.87 (1H, m), 5.26 (1H, m), 5.10 (1H, m), 4.44 (2H, s), 4.33 (1H, m), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.74–3.55 (2H, m), 1.89–1.74 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50 MHz) : δ 159.1, 140.4, 129.8, 129.1, 114.2, 113.7, 72.8, 71.9, 68.0, 55.2, 36.1; ESIMS : m/z 245 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(S)-t-Butyl-((5-((4-Methoxybenzyl)oxy)pent-1-en-3-yl)oxy)dimethylsilane (16): To a solution of **15** (284 mg, 1.27 mmol) in DMF (10 mL) was added imidazole (130 mg, 1.9 mmol) at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mixture was stirred at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min and then TBSCl (230 mg, 1.52 mmol), followed by DMAP (15 mg) were added. The mixture was stirred at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for another 1 h. After completion of reaction, saturated aqueous solution of NH_4Cl was added at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and extracted with diethyl ether (3×10 mL). The organic phase was washed with water and brine, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 97 : 3) to give **16** (405 mg, 95%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.7$ (hexane/EtOAc = 9 : 1); $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +2.1$ (c 1.00, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2935, 2849, 1621, 1518, 1257, 1091 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 7.27 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.87 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 5.81 (1H, m), 5.15 (1H, m), 5.01 (1H, m), 4.49–4.23 (3H, m), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.60–3.43 (2H, m), 1.82–1.71 (2H, m), 0.89 (9H, s), 0.05 (3H, s), 0.30 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50 MHz) : δ 159.0, 141.5, 130.5, 129.2, 113.7, 72.6, 70.7, 66.4, 55.2, 38.0, 25.8, 18.1, -4.3 , -4.9 ; ESIMS : m/z 359 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(S)-3-((t-Butyldimethylsilyl)oxy)pent-4-en-1-ol (17): To a solution of **16** (372 mg, 1.10 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) and H_2O (5 mL), DDQ (377 mg, 1.65 mmol) at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature and then poured into water. The reaction mass was filtered through celite pad and the filtrate was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (2×10 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 (10 mL), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated in vacuum. Flash chromatography (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 90 : 10) afforded alcohol **17** (220 mg, 91%) as a colorless oil. $R_f = 0.3$ (hexane/EtOAc = 8 : 2); $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +10.2$ (c 1.5, CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3365, 2933, 2860, 1620, 1517, 1249 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ

5.85 (1H, m), 5.23 (1H, m), 5.11 (1H, m), 4.43 (1H, m), 3.83 (1H, m), 3.71 (1H, m), 2.55 (1H, brs), 1.86 (1H, m), 1.71 (1H, m), 0.91 (9H, s), 0.10 (3H, s), 0.06 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50 MHz): δ 140.5, 114.4, 73.2, 60.0, 39.0, 25.7, 18.1, -4.4, -5.1; ESIMS: m/z 217 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$.

(S)-3-((*t*-Butyldimethylsilyloxy)pent-4-enoic acid (**5**): To a solution of above alcohol **17** (195 mg, 0.90 mmol) in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (1/1, 4 mL), TEMPO (44 mg, 0.30 mmol) and BAIB (870 mg, 2.7 mmol) were added. After stirring at room temperature for 2 h, the reaction mixture was diluted with CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) and then washed with saturated aqueous $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (10 mL). The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered, and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give the crude carboxylic acid, which was further purified by flash chromatography (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 90 : 10) to give acid **5** (185 mg, 89%) as a colorless oil. R_f = 0.2 (hexane/EtOAc = 6 : 4); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ = +8.3 (c 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2932, 2860, 1717, 1467, 1253, 1090 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 10.61 (1H, brs), 5.85 (1H, m), 5.25 (1H, m), 5.14 (1H, m), 4.58 (1H, m), 2.63–2.43 (2H, m), 0.89 (9H, s), 0.08 (3H, s), 0.06 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50 MHz) : δ 176.3, 139.4, 115.1, 70.5, 43.2, 25.6, 17.9, -4.4, -5.2; ESIMS : m/z 253 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(S)-*(R)*-1-((4*S*,5*S*)-2,2-Dimethyl-5-vinyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)undecan-2-yl-3-((*t*-butyldimethylsilyloxy)pent-4-enoate (**3**): To a solution of acid **5** (115 mg, 0.5 mmol) in dry THF (8 mL) at 0 °C, Et_3N (0.21 mL, 1.5 mmol) and 2,4,6- $\text{Cl}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{COCl}$ (0.16 mL, 1 mmol) were added, and the resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and azeotroped with benzene and the residue was taken up in dry toluene (5 mL). To this mixture at 0 °C a solution of DMAP (182 mg, 1.5 mmol) and alcohol **4** (150 mg, 0.5 mmol) in toluene (5 mL) were added, and the resulting mixture was stirred for 15 min. The reaction mixture was diluted with EtOAc (10 mL), washed with saturated aqueous NH_4Cl (5 mL), and brine (5 mL). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , filtered, concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by CC (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 97 : 3) to give diene **3** (225 mg, 88%) as a colorless oil. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ = -3.1 (c 0.5,

CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2930, 2866, 1737, 1399, 1313, 1219 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 5.94–5.69 (2H, m), 5.37 (1H, m), 5.30–5.18 (2H, m), 5.13–4.99 (2H, m), 4.58 (1H, m), 3.99 (1H, m), 3.71 (1H, m), 2.56 (1H, m), 2.42 (1H, m), 1.81–1.51 (4H, m), 1.40 (3H, s), 1.37 (3H, s), 1.32–1.21 (14H, m), 0.89 (9H, s), 0.88 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 0.07 (3H, s), 0.05 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 170.3, 140.1, 134.8, 119.1, 114.6, 108.8, 82.8, 77.3, 72.0, 70.5, 43.6, 36.5, 34.4, 31.8, 29.6, 29.5, 29.4, 29.2, 27.2, 26.8, 25.8, 24.9, 22.6, 18.1, 14.0, -4.4, -4.8; ESIMS : m/z 533 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(3*aS*,5*R*,9*S*,11*aS*,*E*)-9-((*t*-Butyldimethylsilyloxy)-2,2-dimethyl-5-nonyl-4,5,8,9-tetrahydro-3*aH*-[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-*d*]oxecin-7(11*aH*)-one (**18**): To a solution of diene **3** (100 mg, 0.2 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (120 mL) deoxygenated by argon, Grubbs' 2nd generation catalyst (35 mg, 0.04 mmol) was added and again the mixture was degassed with argon. The mixture was then stirred at reflux for 6 h. After cooling to room temperature, all volatiles were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by CC (silica gel, hexanes : EtOAc = 98 : 2) to give **18** (84 mg, 87%) as a colorless oil. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ = -13.5 (c 0.5, CHCl_3); IR (neat) : 2927, 2855, 1740, 1464, 1373, 1257, 1159, 1057 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 5.93 (1H, m), 5.67 (1H, m), 4.95 (1H, m), 4.70 (1H, m), 4.07 (1H, dd, J 8.9, 8.8 Hz), 3.63 (1H, dd, J 8.7, 8.4 Hz), 2.55 (2H, d, J 3.0 Hz), 2.10–1.82 (2H, m), 1.56–1.37 (2H, m), 1.40 (6H, s), 1.34–1.19 (14H, m), 0.92 (9H, s), 0.89 (3H, t, J 6.5 Hz), 0.12 (3H, s), 0.09 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50 MHz) : δ 168.4, 137.7, 123.2, 107.6, 84.0, 81.7, 72.3, 67.9, 45.0, 36.5, 36.0, 31.7, 29.7, 29.3, 29.0, 27.3, 27.0, 26.8, 25.6, 25.3, 22.5, 18.0, 14.2, -4.9, -5.0; ESIMS : m/z 505 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

(4*S*,7*S*,8*S*,10*R*,*E*)-4,7,8-Trihydroxy-10-nonyl-3,4,7,8,9,10-hexahydro-2*H*-oxecin-2-one; Seimatopolide A (**1**): To a solution of macrolactone **18** (72 mg, 0.15 mmol) in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 : 1, 6 mL), TFA (0.3 mL) was added dropwise at 0 °C. The mixture was slowly warmed to room temperature and stirred for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then quenched with saturated aqueous NaHCO_3 (15 mL) at 0 °C and extracted with EtOAc (2 \times 15 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (10 mL) and dried over Na_2SO_4 . The combined organic phase was concentrated and the resulting

residue was purified by CC (hexane : EtOAc = 30 : 70) to afford **1** (39 mg, 81%) as a colorless solid. $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -37.8$ (*c* 0.05, MeOH); IR (KBr) : 3427, 2919, 2846, 1713, 1659, 1437 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (pyridine-*d*₅, 300 MHz) : δ 6.45 (1H, dd, *J* 15.8, 9.8 Hz), 6.16 (1H, dd, *J* 15.8, 4.2 Hz), 5.14 (1H, m), 4.97 (1H, m), 4.39 (1H, m), 3.96 (1H, m), 2.86 (1H, dd, *J* 11.8, 3.2 Hz), 2.75 (1H, dd, *J* 11.8, 4.0 Hz), 2.33–2.22 (2H, m), 1.69 (1H, m), 1.59 (1H, m), 1.45–1.29 (2H, m), 1.26–1.14 (12H, m), 0.87 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (pyridine-*d*₅, 75 MHz) : δ 170.7, 136.8, 128.2, 79.8, 77.4, 73.5, 67.7, 44.8, 42.6, 37.6, 32.5, 30.4, 30.1, 29.8, 25.7, 23.1, 14.4; ESIMS : *m/z* 351 [M+Na]⁺; HRMS (ESI) : Calcd. for C₁₈H₃₂O₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 351.2142; Found 351.2152.

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